

SYSTEM LEVEL MODELING METHODOLOGY OF APPLICATION SPECIFIC INSTRUCTION SET PROCESSOR (ASIP) USING SYSTEMC

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Abstract: In recent years, the development of application specific instruction set processors (ASIP) is the exclusive domain of the semiconductor houses and core vendors. This is due to the fact that constructing such architecture is a difficult assignment that needs skilled knowledge in distinct domains: application software development tools, processor hardware implementation, and system integration and verification. To specify the design and implementation of such systems and incorporate the functionality implemented in both hardware and software forms, we are compelled to move on from traditional Hardware Description Languages (HDLs). Since C and C++ are dominant languages used by chip architects, system engineers and software engineers today, we believe that a C++ based approach to hardware modeling is necessary. This will enable codesign, providing a more natural solution to partitioning functionality between hardware and software. In this paper, we discuss a design approach of SystemC (a C++ class library) for ASIP at the system-level which provides necessary features for modeling design hierarchy, concurrency and reactivity in hardware. To exemplify and validate the method we employed it to the design of a 32-bit ASIP for Hindi Text-to-Speech Synthesis developed by CEERI, Pilani (INDIA).

Keywords : ASIP , System and, System Level Design

1. Introduction

Due to the ever-decreasing feature size of today's semiconductor processes, the cost of a mask set has already crossed the one-million-dollar line. To pay off this investment, a design must be applicable for multiple purposes. The flexibility needed to achieve this is commonly provided by programmable elements. A unique opportunity to trade off the flexibility of general-purpose processor cores against the performance of hard-wired logic is offered by application-

specific instruction-set processors (ASIPs). The instruction set of an ASIP is dedicated towards a particular class of applications by compound instructions that speed up critical parts of the applications without compromising the flexibility of the processor in its application domain [1, 12, 13,19].

Due to the diversity of the application domains that ASIPs are specialized in, it demands greater attention during synthesis tool development [2, 3, 11, 14]. It is the function of the synthesis tool to offer abstraction from the low level details of the hardware, in order to make the implementation of algorithms a tractable problem for the human programmer. It merely shifts the burden from the application developer to the synthesis tool designer. Generally, there are two types of approaches by the commercially

Fig. 1: SystemC Language Architecture [16]

supported flows: the tool oriented design flow or a language oriented design flow. Here we are only discussing the language oriented design flow.

The goal of the language-oriented approach is to create an environment where implementations can be realized in a ‘stress-free’ programming language; it makes some sense to assume such a language from the outset, and to implement it in a top-down fashion. it is summarized as follows:

1. Design or choose a programming language which provides behavioral semantics for the constraints of the algorithms
2. Generate transformation schemes for each of the language’s behavioral constructs[15].

SystemC one of the languages which is capable of providing all the requirements for the ASIP architecture exploration. It is an emerging standard modeling platform based on C++ which it allows describing a fully functional model that incorporates design constraints and has a simulation environment for an integrated validation against a set of test vectors. More of its feature is discussed in section 2. The work presented in this paper refers to an optimized system level framework for implementation of an ASIP using SystemC platform. In Section 3, we describe the architecture design overview of ASIP of Hindi text-to-speech conversion (developed by IC Design Group, CEERI, Pilani, INDIA). In section 4, we illustrate the SystemC implementation methodology of the said processor. In Section 5, we show the testing environments and results. Finally, Section 6 draws the conclusion.

2. SystemC LANGUAGE

SystemC has been initiated by the Open SystemC Initiative (OSCI). OSCI is a non-profit association that has been found by several industrial, academical and individual partners. The aim of OSCI is the standardization of SystemC as an open source standard for system level design. Since the SystemC library is open source, various kinds of modifications and extension libraries are publicly available, too [15,6,5,8,20]. Fig. 1 summarizes the SystemC language architecture and Fig. 2 describes the design environment of SystemC .

The system description language SystemC provides hardware constructs, implemented in a C++ class library. The hardware models specified using SystemC can be compiled on a large number of supported architectures using a standard C++ compiler [16, 9]. The compiled executables can be cycle accurate simulations as well as untimed algorithmic descriptions of the given design. The executable specifications can be used for evaluation, debugging and refinement purposes without the usage of a commercial simulator. Depending on the abstraction level the simulation speed can be a multiple of a functional equivalent HDL model. Because of its unrestricted C++ conformance each SystemC model can be combined with other

Fig. 2: SystemC in a C++ development

software libraries. This allows system engineers to take advantage of HW/SW Co-Design and to refine their SoC designs with a high level of flexibility. Another benefit of SystemC, coming with its C++ conformance, is a wide range of abstraction levels that can be used to simplify huge system designs [21]. Complex communication protocols and control logic can easily be separated from functional parts of the specification. For this reason SystemC offers techniques that can raise or lower the level of abstraction. The TLM library implements such a technique to support SystemC’s efficient refinement methodology [7].

SystemC combines HDL typical features, like concurrency as it appears in hardware, with software paradigms, like object orientation. These features distinguish SystemC from VHDL, Verilog and SystemVerilog and enable system description capabilities. SystemC allows real polymorphism which includes the application of arbitrary memory access using pointers and dynamic memory allocation. Even the concept of virtual functions that binds overloaded class members to function pointers, is applicable in system descriptions. Special benefits, like channels, make SystemC ideal for describing complex communication protocols and their easy reuse.

3. Architecture Design of the Asip

In this section, we describe the design of the ASIP (Fig. 3) developed by the CEERI, Pilani, INDIA [4, 18]. It can serve as an efficient platform for embedded systems running the parametric speech synthesizer in portable/mobile applications. An application-friendly instruction set and a supporting micro-architecture have been created that permit execution of the parametric speech synthesizer in real-time using a relatively small gate count and memory size and potentially low power consumption following the design philosophy of [4]. It had an execution unit following with a number of application specific dedicated functional blocks—some with combinational architectures and others with their own optimized sequential architectures and associated controllers. These functional units and the integer and floating-point memory blocks of required size along with the necessary temporary registers were connected through a single bus for transfer of data among them. This approach provided a mechanism for interpreting an application-specific, user-friendly instruction set onto sufficiently high-level functional units by moving data to them over the bus and triggering them.

The 32-bit instruction-set of the processor was designed to provide several application-specific, user-friendly, 'high-level' instructions which implemented frequently-repeating, logically meaningful, computational patterns specific to

the application-formant-based parametric speech synthesis. These include instructions like:

- 1) resonator: which computes the function of as second-order resonator.
- 2) setabc: which computes the three resonator coefficients — given the frequency of resonance and the resonance bandwidth.
- 3) rand12: which generates a sequence of 12 pseudorandom numbers.
- 4) exp: which computes the value of the exponential function for its operand.
- 5) sin-cos: which computes the values of the sine and cosine functions for its operand.

Fig. 3: CEERI ASIP [18]

Besides these instructions, a number of low-level, general-purpose instructions are also included for addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, data-moves, and type conversion of operands. The program control instructions include various conditional branch instructions (based on results of relational operators on variables), instructions for supporting loop constructs, and for subroutine calls and returns. The processor's instruction set has a set of 44 instructions

4. Model Implementation

Fig. 4 illustrates the basic structure of framework of the methodology. we start with the traditional methods used to capture the customer requirements, a Product Requirements Document (PRD). From the PRD, a ASIP-SAM (ASIP System Architecture Model) is developed. The ASIP-SAM development effort may cause changes or refinement to the PRD. In an algorithmic intensive system, the ASIP-SAM will be used to refine the system algorithms.

Fig. 4: Basic Structure of Framework of Methodology

The ASIP-SAM development consists of breaking the processor’s functionality into a set of instructions. A component’s functionality represents all possible behaviors that the components can assume, with behavior meaning the set of actions that the component performs during the execution of an application. The objective of ASIP-SAM development is to capture the specification of the system in terms of design behavior with the least amount of

design work. This first step hides the complexity of the processor’s internal implementation behind the simple interface offered by the instruction set. There is a tradeoff in selecting the right set of instructions: having many fine-grained instructions can lead to greater accuracy, but it requires a longer simulation time than having fewer coarse-grained instructions.

The next stage TLM Refinement involves simulating the application program and extracting a trace file for the processor. A trace is the sequence of instructions/data items a component executes during its simulation. The aim is to estimate the component’s switching activity.

The last step (SystemC RTL Model Development) consists of mapping the instructions requested by the various tasks performed by the component into abstract functional units that are used to estimate complexity—that is, gate count and timing delay. Given switching activity and complexity, the framework can also compute the component’s power per instruction and execution time per instruction.

To Solve the equation $3 * e^2 - 4.5 * e^6 + 7.2$

```

1100000000001000000000100000000 // EXP #4, #4
0010110000000100000000000000000 // MULTFF #4, #0
11000000000001010000000101000000 // EXP #5, #5
00101100000001010000000001000000 // MULTFF #4, #0
00001000000001000000000101000000 ADD FF #4,#5
00001100000001000000000010000000 // ADDFC #4, #2
    
```

Fig. 5 Object Code with its Assembly Pneumonics

Fig. 6: Waveform Result

5. Results

The design is implemented using WindowsXP as platform and Microsoft Visual Studio 2005 as simulator for SystemC whereas the Waveforms are seen through BlueHDL VCD Viewer. In this framework, we simulated ten different application programs and validated the functionality. One of the test program and its result are shown in the Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we presented the SystemC processor design platform – a framework for the design of application specific integrated processors. The platform supports the architecture designer in different domains: architecture exploration, implementation, application software design and system integration/verification. An ASIP developed by CEERI, Pilani, was completely realized using this novel design methodology – from specification to implementation.

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